

Specialised logging trailer - solution for efficient use of transportation resources

Introduction

Currently there is trend that allowed total loads for trucks on public roads are increasing. That allows transportation of bigger volumes per truck and generates less pollution to environment. OG has developed a version of a long logging trailer that is convenient in use also for transportation of short logs thanks to specific construction of bunks that can be moved closer to lifting crane and away from that when cradles are filled.

Innovative technical solution of the long logging trailer provides possibility to fill it 100% also with shorter logs. This is mostly impossible with standard long trailers. Problem is that it is very difficult or impossible to balance short log and load it to far end of a long trailer. You need to hold the log at one end and it is too difficult for hydraulics. In this innovative trailer bunks are movable. Empty cradles can be moved forward, shorter logs loaded closer to the crane and filled cradle moved to far end of the trailer afterwards. Thus trailer can be filled 100% also with shorter logs. Full load results in lower CO2 emissions per cubic meter of transported timber.

Lessons learned

Question that may arise: Why are such trailers not available widely already now? This is innovation that arose following trends that bigger and bigger loads are being allowed on public roads. This is long trailer and can pick up what is required at the road side only. So far logging trucks often are double trailers where truck has a manipulator for loading timber. Truck may leave a trailer on the road, drive deeper to the forest, pick up logs, transport them to the road side and re-load to the trailer, then drive back and load up another portion on the truck itself. Finally go back to main road, attach trailer and transport cargo to destination point. Nowadays often companies use more efficient specialised off-road tractors for transporting logs to the roadside.

Further contacts

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<https://youtu.be/OeNFJd3EFFF>

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

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